

THE EFFECT OF IVF ON POSTPARTUM HEMORRHAGE IN OOCYTE DONATION COMPARED TO PREGNANCY ACHIEVED THROUGH NATURAL CONCEPTION

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ABSTRACT

Oocyte donation (OD) enables an increasing number of women to conceive. However, OD pregnancies have a high risk for pregnancy complications, such as severe postpartum hemorrhage (PPH). To provide an overview of current existing knowledge on the risk of developing PPH in OD pregnancies, and its possible pathophysiology, we conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis.

The literature search yielded eighteen eligible studies for the systematic review; seventeen were included in the meta-analysis. The meta-analysis showed an overall significant risk of PPH in OD versus AO-IVF/ICSI pregnancies and NC pregnancies, although heterogeneity was present. All sub-analyses using different definitions of PPH as well as sensitivity analyses for adjusted ORs and low risk of bias showed similar result. This systematic review and meta-analysis confirms and provides more robust evidence compared to previous meta- the increased risk of PPH in OD pregnancies when compared with both NC pregnancies and AO-IVF/ICSI pregnancies.

Introduction. Oocyte donation (OD) is an assisted reproductive technique (ART) that enables women with diminished ovarian function to conceive. Since the first live birth after a successful OD pregnancy was reported before, the use of OD has increased significantly. This increase could be attributed, among other reasons, to the postponement of pregnancy to advanced maternal age or expanding indications for OD use, such as shared lesbian motherhood with reception of oocytes from the partner (ROPA).

With the increasing numbers of OD pregnancies, various studies on obstetric outcomes report a higher incidence of pregnancy complications when comparing OD pregnancies with naturally conceived (NC), autologous oocyte in vitro fertilization (AO-IVF) and autologous intracytoplasmic sperm injection (AO-ICSI) pregnancies. Women face a significantly higher risk of developing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, such as pregnancy induced hypertension and preeclampsia. Incidence of caesarean section (CS) and postpartum

haemorrhage (PPH) also appears to be increased in OD pregnancies, even after adjustment for confounding factors such as maternal age, Body Mass Index (BMI), and parity.

Additionally, the reported incidence of PPH varies widely, possibly due to the lack of a universally used definition of PPH regarding the amount of blood loss and a set timeframe. Researchers currently use a variety of definitions and thresholds, ranging from 500 ml to 1000 ml blood loss, depending on mode of delivery. The reported incidence of PPH also varies because of a multiplicity of measuring methods. All used methods, including visual estimation and weighing of used equipment, are prone to a certain level of variation, or are not quantifiable. Considering the severity of PPH-related consequences, including thromboembolic events, the need for hysterectomy and even death, consensus on PPH as an independent risk factor in OD pregnancies needs to be established to take adequate and timely (preventive) interventions. In addition, further insight into the potential pathophysiological mechanisms, such as placental pathologies, underlying PPH in OD pregnancies is essential for improving preventative strategies. This systematic review therefore aims to provide an overview of the risk of developing PPH in OD pregnancies. This will allow evaluation of current practices and identification of knowledge gaps for future research.

Materials and methods. We included studies with a cohort or case-control study design that reported on adverse maternal or obstetric outcomes, with PPH, placenta accreta, placenta increta or retained placenta as one of the outcome measures. We excluded studies that lacked a comparison between OD pregnancies and autologous pregnancies, as well as studies exclusively reporting on patients with chromosomal abnormalities, such as Turner's syndrome, or uterine anomalies. Additionally, studies with other study designs (i.e. case reports or series, letters, or review articles) and manuscripts written in languages other than English or Dutch were excluded.

Data was extracted independently by two authors and compared, any discrepancies data interpretation were resolved through consensus among the researchers. In cases where no agreement could be reached, the opinion of a third observer (E.L.) was sought to achieve consensus. The following data were extracted from the selected studies: study design, country, period of inclusion, number of participants, exclusion criteria, control group(s) and outcome measures along with their definitions and corresponding effect measures. If the definition of PPH was missing from the manuscripts, the first corresponding author of the study was contacted through email.

The primary outcome measure is defined as PPH, which consists of total blood loss after vaginal or CS delivery, as defined by the authors of each study. Secondary outcome measures that could postulate the severity of the reported PPH were also extracted and included the need for therapy (such as uterotonics, manual placenta extraction, blood transfusion), surgical intervention (embolization, uterine suture, hysterectomy), intensive care admission or death. To hypothesize the cause of PPH, various placental pathologies were also incorporated as secondary outcome measures, including placenta praevia, placental abruption, placenta accreta, and placental retention. To ensure sufficient data-collection of these rare outcomes, placenta accreta and retained placenta have been added to the literature search and eligibility criteria

Results. The included articles presented varying definitions of post-partum haemorrhage (PPH). Six studies defined PPH as blood loss exceeding or equal to 1000 ml, with only one study including a time restriction of blood loss within 24 hours after delivery. Two studies defined PPH as blood loss exceeding 500 ml, without a time-sensitive restriction, one of which also established a separate group for blood loss greater than 1000 ml. Two studies defined PPH as blood loss exceeding 500 ml for vaginal delivery, and exceeding 1000 ml for CS, one of those also defined a separated subgroup for severe PPH when blood loss exceeded 1000 ml in vaginal deliveries. Two studies, defined PPH as requiring additional therapy. One study distinguished mild PPH (500-1000 ml), moderate PPH (>1000-1500 ml) and major PPH (>1500 ml).

Discussion. Pregnancies conceived after oocyte donation (OD) have been suggested to be associated with a higher risk of specific pregnancy complications, such as severe postpartum haemorrhage (PPH). In this systematic review and meta-analysis, we included studies that investigated the incidence of PPH, comparing OD pregnancies with autologous pregnancies. Seventeen studies could be included in the meta-analysis and confirmed that OD is associated with an increased risk of PPH when compared to AO-IVF/ICSI pregnancies (OR 2.32 (95% CI 1.88-2.87)) and when compared with NC pregnancies (OR 3.15 (95% CI 2.01-4.94)). Although the World Health Organization (WHO) defines PPH as exceeding 500 ml, the included studies used various definitions. ("WHO Guidelines Approved by the Guidelines Review Committee," 2012) Therefore, sub-analyses were performed for the different definitions of PPH, which showed similar risk estimates that were significantly increased for the OD population. These definitions included PPH as blood loss exceeding 1000 ml, blood loss exceeding 500 ml and the requirement of additional therapy. Two studies defined PPH by the requirement of additional therapy PPH, though it remained unclear what type of additional treatment was necessary, which would have been indicative of the severity of PPH.

In general, the methodological quality of the included studies was high, as ten out of eighteen studies showed low overall risk of bias (ROB) according to the ROBINS-I tool. Even though the ROBINS-I tool is likely the best available tool to assess the ROB, outcomes of the assessment might have been different if other confounders had been selected beforehand. We selected primary and secondary confounders based on previous research that documented risk factors for developing PPH, though these risk factors are not yet fully understood. The possibility of residual confounding remains, due to heterogeneity present in the baseline differences between the patient populations, as well as varying definitions of PPH, reflected by the high I² statistic. While some heterogeneity is unavoidable, this meta-analysis provides more robust evidence compared to previous meta-analyses, primarily due to the inclusion of a higher number of studies. The additional analyses of the separated definitions of PPH lower the remaining heterogeneity and allow for more comparable outcomes, helping clinicians assess the risk based on the definition most relevant to their centre. Furthermore, this expanded dataset improves generalizability of our study outcomes, as studies were included from many different types of health facilities across Europe. Still, the main analysis using all studies, consists of different definitions of PPH, so heterogeneity remains present. Additionally, the presence of information bias and selection bias remains possible, as no

individual patient data was available, precise measurements of blood loss remain unknown and in some cases the centre of inclusion (midwifery or hospital) was unknown.

Previous research on hypertensive complications in OD pregnancies indicate that the development of this complication is related to the number of fetal-maternal HLA class II mismatches. In addition, a significantly higher number of HLA matches between mother and child was shown in uncomplicated OD pregnancies than expected by chance. However, in this current study we were not able to confirm that the increased risk is conclusively explained by abnormal placentation, as there was only a small number of studies that reported on the placental pathologies of interest, most exposure groups within study populations were relatively small, and placental abnormalities including placenta accreta are rare findings. Studies were likely underpowered to show any differences for this secondary outcome measure as can be deduced from the broad confidence intervals that resulted from the statistical analysis. Further research is necessary to adequately investigate the possible correlation between abnormal placentation in OD pregnancy and the subsequent risk of PPH. Specifically, immunogenetic factors, such as number of HLA mismatching and the endometrium preparation protocol for frozen embryo transfer should be taken into account. Additionally, research into immunohistochemical factors, including microscopic abnormalities in placental tissue and the presence of different immune cells, is essential.

In conclusion, this systematic review and meta-analysis confirms the increased risk for the development of PPH in OD pregnancies when compared with autologous pregnancies, highlighting the need for further research regarding PPH in OD pregnancies. Additionally, we emphasize the need for a clinically relevant, universally applicable, and acceptable definition of PPH to facilitate comparison, interpretation, and extrapolation of internationally performed research. Acknowledging OD as an independent risk factor for the development of PPH should alert health care professionals for adequate management and prevention of PPH-related complications..